

THE APPEARANCE OF FATIGUE STRIATIONS IN THE SEM

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SUMMARY

Fatigue striations are the characteristic fracture morphologies after fatigue loading. It was found that the striations are formed in steps. A new approach for the contrast origin is given for a correct interpretation. The correlation between occurrence of the striations and crack growth direction was identified.

Keywords: fatigue, fatigue striations, microfractography, CFRP, SEM

Introduction

Microfractography is an essential option for the characterisation of materials. This technique is commonly used to interpret the fracture behaviour of metals but work on microfractography of fibre reinforced plastics was not started until the early 1970s. Although this is still an area of study under development, basic knowledge is already available. For example, specialists from the European aerospace industry compiled a fracture catalogue within the GARTEUR program [1, 2]. As well as a harmonised nomenclature, basic fracture morphologies and failure mechanisms are described in the catalogue.

In 1980, Franz described the existence of fatigue striations as characteristic fracture morphology of fibre reinforced materials under mode I (tension) fatigue loading [3]. He assumed that the formation of the striations took place in steps and proposed an explanation for their appearance in the SEM. Since then, a large body of research into fatigue fracture morphologies has been carried out by the working group Physical Analysis / Failure Analysis at EADS Innovation Works and by other authors. Nevertheless, relatively little published work can be found on fatigue fracture morphologies and this leaves many questions unanswered [2-14]. The emergence of fatigue striations has been established in a multitude of materials and under different loading conditions.

This paper will present the appearance of the fatigue striations in the SEM. The possible locations of the striations on the fracture surface will be described. The formation of the

striations will be shown as a function of the material and different loading conditions, as well as distinctions in the detection. A revised explanation is given for the appearance of the striations in the SEM.

The occurrence of fatigue striations on the fracture surface

Fatigue striations are lamellar, more or less distinct markings which run perpendicular to the fracture direction inside fibre imprints or resin areas. Due to their low height-to-distance ratio, they can only be identified at high tilt angles relative to the primary electron beam in the SEM. Unless otherwise indicated, all pictures within this paper were taken at a tilt angle of 45° with the specimen being tilted backwards.

The typical appearance of fatigue striations in fibre imprints can be seen in Fig. 1. When describing the striations, a distinction has to be drawn between fatigue striations, which have a certain width and represent the crack growth during one load cycle, and the fatigue lines, which are the dividing lines between the striations. No direct correlation between striation spacing and crack growth is given due to the complex state of loading in the anisotropic composite material. The formation of the striations also varies considerably according to the loading mode and R-ratio. Fatigue striations have a shape which projects out of the fracture plane, preferably in the form of steps and the fatigue lines represent the short, steep flanks of the steps. The local fracture direction is thereby oriented along the steps, i.e. the crack runs upwards [2 ,4, 9].

Figure 1: Fatigue striations in the fibre imprint.

The occurrence of fatigue striations inside the fibre imprints is by far the most frequent case. This was explained by the action of the fracture growth mechanism with the primary crack front propagated inside the fibre-matrix interface (“finger growth”) [5]. This mechanism occurs because the load transmission takes place over the fibres and needs a certain stress intensity for the formation of the fatigue striations.

Consequently, the occurrence of fatigue striations in the resin areas between the fibres is not very common. They are treated as secondary fractures, which grow fan-shaped

inside the circumjacent resin matrix, starting at secondary crack initiation points on the fibre surface (Fig. 2).

Figure 2: Fatigue striations in the resin area between the fibres [12].

The secondary fatigue fractures in the resin area between the fibres can be found mainly in woven reinforced specimens and in thick specimens. The occurrence in the latter is explained by increased stress intensity due to higher stiffness [4].

Fig. 3 shows typical fatigue fracture planes in resin pockets. Resin pockets are typical flaws inside composite materials. Depending on the lay-up of the material, e.g. RTM preform materials, they are intrinsic to the material and cannot be avoided.

Resin pockets act as points of crack initiation due to the local step in stiffness between load transmitting fibres and resin reach area. Where there is predamage, fatigue crack growth in the resin pocket is treated as a secondary crack. If there is no predamage, it is treated as part of the fracture initiation phase [9].

Figure 3: Fatigue striations in resin pockets.

An exception to the occurrence of fatigue striations on the fracture surface is presented by the formation under pure mode II (shear) load (Fig. 4). The characteristic fracture

morphologies of fatigue under mode II loading are rollers. These are formed due to the shear load at 45° to the loading direction. It was possible to show that in the initial stage of the fracture this is the opening of the 45° crack, local mode I (tension) load is given. This leads to the formation of fatigue striations on the roller surface, which can consequently be regarded as secondary structures.

Figure 4: Fatigue striations as the initial stage of the roller formation under mode II loading [12].

The appearance of fatigue striations in the SEM

As referred to above, the majority of fatigue striations can be found inside fibre imprints on the fracture surface.

Apart from the familiar fact that striations can only be seen at high tilt angles, their appearance in the SEM is dependent on the azimuth angle. Fig. 5 shows the same fatigue area with the distinctly formed striations inside fibre imprints at two azimuth angles. At an angle of 0° (left), the fatigue lines appear as white lines, after rotating through 180° the fatigue striations are characterised by dark lines.

Figure 5: Fatigue striations inside fibre imprints: both pictures show the same area on the surface under two different azimuth angles – left: 0° , right: 180°

This behaviour of the striations together with their small height/distance ratio makes it rather difficult to detect them in the SEM.

In contrast to Franz [3], the fatigue striations in resin areas have the appearance of steps (Fig. 6), but are typically not distinctly formed. Depending on the matrix material and the local load, the two flanks of the steps can shift to a more or less wavelike form (Fig. 7). Nevertheless, fatigue striations in resin pockets are relatively easy to detect. Due to the frequently rounded fracture surface of the resin pockets, there is typically at least one area which is in the contrast angle for detecting the striations.

Figure 6: Fatigue striations in a resin pocket (matrix resin: RTM6).

Investigations on CFRP with toughened matrices (micro-phase separated rubber particles in Epoxy resin) indicated that the toughening of the matrix also influences the formation and therefore the appearance of the fatigue striations. Fig. 7 shows the appearance of fatigue striations in a resin pocket of toughened matrix. It is noticeable, that the rubber/resin interface failure occurs in the form of debonding of the toughening rubber particles.

Figure 7: Fatigue striations in a resin pocket of a CFRP with toughened matrix

The latter cannot be found in fibre imprints on fatigue fracture areas of the toughened matrix. This may be due to the fibres being a third phase, where the interface is an area of local irregularities comprising adhesion to the matrix and near adjacent rubber particles.

Fig. 8 shows fatigue striations in fibre imprints of a toughened matrix. This picture shows that no distinct formation of the fatigue striations took place. The plastic deformation, which is normally only determined by the state of stress directly at the crack tip, is on a broader area influenced by local differences in plasticity of the resin and irregularities of the adhesion. At lower magnifications, the striations appear as nearly closed lines (Fig. 6, left). Higher magnifications show morphologies perpendicular to the fracture direction which are not closed.

Figure 8: Fatigue striations in fibre imprints of a CFRP with toughened matrix

The indistinct formation of the striations can also be found in untoughened matrix material like RTM6. This is caused by the type of reinforcement and the local load conditions. Depending on the type of reinforcement, the local fatigue crack growth can be arrested so that striations can only be found in few areas. In this case, the striations are typically only indistinctly formed. The local load also influences the formation, in the same way as the relative position of the fibre to the main load direction or the proportion of shear loading.

Investigations into specimens loaded under different frequencies showed no influence on the basic morphology of the fatigue striations up to 600 Hz. The increase in amplitude during the test and hence the increase in the crack growth rate also exert no influence on the stepped morphology of the fatigue striations [4, 9, 10].

Fig. 9 shows fatigue striations in a resin pocket of a specimen loaded with 600Hz. Crack propagation appears here at different fracture planes which run in the direction of fracture and propagate into each other in scarp formations. This is caused by a high local mode III (torsion) share. The blurred demarcations of the scaly structure stand out as a wavy form and represent the cyclic component of the fracture morphology as fatigue striations.

Figure 9: Fatigue striations in resin pocket under high frequency load and mode III (torsion) share.

Fig. 10 shows fatigue striations inside fibre imprints of a specimen loaded under 600Hz. The striations are formed very distinctly. An azimuth rotation of 180° was carried out in order to demonstrate the effect of the inversion of the fatigue lines referred to above.

Figure 10: Fatigue striations in fibre imprints under high frequency load. Azimuth rotation of 180°.

Discussion and Conclusion

Fatigue striations can mostly be found in fibre imprints or resin pockets. Striations can only be found under certain conditions within resin areas between the fibres. All results of microfractographic investigations on cyclically loaded specimens indicate that fatigue striations are steplike structures projecting out of the fracture plane.

It is therefore necessary to correct the common explanation provided in the literature for the appearance of fatigue striations in the SEM [2, 4, 11, 12]. In the SEM, the primary electron beam is the “eye”. Undercuts cannot therefore be reached by the beam and cannot be seen as dark lines. The location of the detector only exerts an influence on the “lighting” of the picture.

The bright and dark lines of the fatigue striations can only be explained by the variation in brightness of differently tilted planes. The secondary electron (SE) contrast is determined by the amount of secondary electrons emitted. With increasing inclination of the specimen surface to the primary electron beam and on etches (edge effect), the absolute emission area of secondary electrons increases and the surface appears brighter. Thus, the secondary electron contrast in the SEM originates mainly due to local differences of the angles between the primary electron beam and the specimen surface.

The appearance of fatigue striations in the SEM is illustrated in Fig. 11. The dark fatigue lines can hence be explained by differences in the local inclination of the planes to the primary electron beam. The bright striations are caused by the edge effect (compare to Fig. 10).

Figure 11: The appearance of fatigue striations in the SEM.

The contrast angle is the angle where two differently inclined planes can be distinguished and the following constraint is given:

$$\left(\angle_{flank1} - \angle_{tilt}\right) - \left(\angle_{flank2} + \angle_{tilt}\right) \geq \angle_{contrast} \quad (1)$$

Thus, the striations must also be visible at small tilt angles if $\angle_{flank1} <</>> \angle_{flank2}$. This was evident [9]. In this case, the SEM needs a detector to detect a very small SE rate due to the dependence of the contrast angle on resolution and sensitivity.

Investigations into the appearance of the striations showed their occurrence correlated with the crack growth direction. Fig. 10 demonstrates that the curvature of the striations always points in the direction of the crack growth. It is necessary to take both characteristics into account in order to interpret the fatigue crack history correctly: the kind of striation forming and the appearance in the SEM.

The appearance of the fatigue striations in the SEM also clearly demonstrates the need to indicate the tilt angle and the tilt direction of the specimen. Otherwise, it is not possible to arrive at a correct interpretation of the given surface structures. In particular, a lack of information frequently leads to misinterpretations of fracture surfaces.

Conclusion

This paper presents the varying appearances and formations of fatigue striations. Fatigue striations can generally be found in fibre imprints or resin pockets. Inside the resin areas between the fibres, striations can only be found under certain conditions. Overall, fatigue striations are steplike structures projecting out of the fracture plane. The inversion of the striations was explained by the elucidation of the contrast origin in the SEM. Hence, the correct formation of the striations can be seen. The correlation between curvature of the striations and crack growth direction was identified. It was also demonstrated that the tilt angle and the tilt direction of the specimen needs to be identified in order to interpret the fracture surface correctly.

The necessary local loading conditions and formation mechanisms of the fatigue striations have deliberately not been discussed. This will be the subject of a further paper.

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